

On Munjistin. Part I.

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The main constituents of the colouring matter of madder, both Indian and European, can be divided into two groups: (a) hydroxy-anthraquinones containing only hydroxyl groups like alizarin, purpurin, purpuroxanthin and (b) those containing hydroxy groups along with methyl (or carboxyl) groups like rubiadin, munjistin pseudopurpurin, etc. The constitution of all these compounds is known with the solitary exception of munjistin.

Stenhouse first discovered this compound in the Indian madder, *Rubia munjista* (*Annalen*, 1864, **130**, 325) and suggested that it was purpuroxanthin carboxylic acid. This was confirmed by Schunk and Römer (*Ber.*, 1877, **10**, 172, 790). They showed that it gives phthalic acid on oxidation and when heated gives purpuroxanthin and carbon dioxide. The structure of munjistin is, therefore, either (I) or (II).

I

II

A review of the constitutions of naturally occurring anthraquinone derivatives whose structures have been correctly determined reveals the fact that invariably the methyl (or carboxyl) group is in a β -position. Not a single exception to this rule has been hitherto found in nature. So it seemed probable that munjistin contains the carboxyl group in β -position; or, in other words that it is the oxidation product of rubiadin. We therefore attempted the synthesis of the substance (I) by the oxidation of rubiadin.

The synthesis of rubiadin as carried out in this laboratory (*This Journal*, 1928, **5**, 25) starting with dioxy-*p*-toluic acid gives an extremely poor yield. Attempts were made to increase the yield by

varying the concentration of fuming sulphuric acid used for sulphonation and the temperature but to no avail. The preparation of dioxy-*p*-toluic acid was then attempted over the dinitro compound, but without success. Recourse was then taken to the following scheme analogous to the synthesis of alizarin, purpurin and purpuroxanthin from β -oxyanthraquinone.

In order to ascertain the best methods of oxidation of hydroxymethylantraquinones with hydroxyl group contiguous to the methyl group it was also considered desirable to perform some preliminary experiments with easily available hydroxymethylantraquinones having such structure and we thought of preparing 1-hydroxy-2-methylantraquinone by condensing *o*-cresol with phthalic anhydride according to the method of Bently, Gardner and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 163). They had condensed phthalic anhydride and *o*-cresol in two different ways and got two

different compounds. By condensing the two compounds in boric acid medium they obtained 1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone, m.p. 184°; and by condensing *o*-cresol methyl ether with phthalic anhydride in carbon disulphide using aluminium chloride as the condensing agent they obtained another anthraquinone (m.p. over 300°) and which they considered to be 1-methyl-2-hydroxyanthraquinone (*ibid*).

Attempt was made to obtain 1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone by condensing *o*-cresol and phthalic anhydride with boric acid but the yield was extremely poor.

Ullmann (*Ber.*, 1919, 52, 2105) had obtained two benzoyl-benzoic acids by condensing *o*-cresol and phthalic anhydride in acetylene tetrachloride medium and this experiment was repeated by us. Two benzoyl-benzoic acids were obtained, one melting at 223° and another at 196°. The latter acid (m. p. 196°) was identical with the one obtained by Weizmann by condensing phthalic anhydride and *o*-cresol in presence of boric acid and it was clearly the result of *ortho* condensation.

The other product melting at 223°—and this was the main product—must therefore be the result of *para*-condensation, and should have the structure (III).

The benzoyl benzoic acid when heated with sulphuric acid at 100° gave an anthraquinone melting at 184° (Formula VIII) identical with that obtained by Weizmann. Curiously enough the benzoyl benzoic acid (Formula III) gave on heating with sulphuric acid at 100° an anthraquinone melting at 211-12°. No such compound has been described in the literature. On methylation however and heating for 20 minutes at 155° in sulphuric acid, the same benzoyl benzoic acid (Formula III) gave a methoxyanthraquinone melting at 184° as well as its demethylation product, an anthraquinone melting at 299° as observed by Weizmann.

It may be noted that the benzoic acid (III) can give rise to two different anthraquinones.

and these (IV and IX) must represent the formula of the two different anthraquinones, m.p. 211-212° and 299° respectively.

Weizmann had ascribed formula (IX) to his compound melting over 300° on the ground that Froude (*Annalen*, 1882, 202, 165) had obtained a compound melting at 262° by condensing phthalic anhydride and *o*-cresol with sulphuric acid and had given to it the formula (IV). Bistrzycki and Zen-Ruffinen (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 369) have synthesised the same anthraquinone, m.p. 299° *via* anthrone and from the mode of preparation they say that it must have formula (IV). They had also established the identity of Froude's compound with this by comparison of their acetyl derivatives. To decide which of the two anthraquinones melting at 211-12° and melting at 299° has the structure (IV), the compound melting at 299° was distilled with zinc dust. The product obtained was found to be β -methylanthracene which proves beyond dispute the constitution (IV) for the anthraquinone melting at 299°. The anthraquinone melting at 211-212° is therefore 1-methyl-2-hydroxyanthraquinone. The compound obtained by Froude (*loc. cit.*) which softened at 182° (1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone melts at 184°) and melted at 260-262°, with partial decomposition was evidently a mixture of three anthraquinones, 1-hydroxy-2-methyl-, 1-methyl-2-hydroxy-, and 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone.

The 2-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (IV), gave on alkali fusion, 3-methylalizarin identical with the compound obtained by Froude (*loc. cit.*).

The crude methyl alizarin was oxidised according to the method of D.-R.P. No. 260765. The product obtained could not be crystallised. On sublimation red crystals resembling purpurin were obtained, melting at 234-35°. The compound is identical with the methylpurpurin prepared by Eder and Manoukian by nitrating 1-oxy-3-methylanthraquinone and replacing the nitro group by,

hydroxyl group by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, 9, 51). The yield of 3-methylpurpurin was very poor and though attempt was made to reduce it to rubiadin (VI) with alkaline stannous chloride no product could be isolated.

Preliminary experiments on the oxidation of hydroxy methyl anthraquinones were made with 1-methyl-2-oxyanthraquinone. The idea was to see which oxidising agent would work best with the compounds having hydroxyl and methyl groups in adjoining positions, their resistance to oxidation being well known. Chromic acid was first tried but the compound completely broke up even when the reaction was carried out in acetic acid and acetic anhydride media. Some work of Noyes (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 52) suggested that such compounds might be oxidised by alkaline ferricyanide. On boiling with potassium hydroxide and potassium ferricyanide, a product was obtained which was distinctly acid but this could not be crystallised by any means whatsoever.

The case with which alizarin passed to purpurin suggested that natural munjistin may be oxidised to purpurin carboxylic acid thereby throwing light on its constitution. Extraction of natural munjistin is a very laborious and lengthy process and only 0.4 gms. was obtained by working up 10 lbs. of powdered root of *B. Munjista*. When 0.3 gm. was subjected to oxidation a red mass was obtained in such a small quantity that it could not be purified.

The experiments are being continued.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of 2'-Hydroxy-3'-methyl-2-benzoylbenzoic acid (VII) and 4'-Hydroxy-3'-methyl-2-benzoylbenzoic acid (III).

o-Cresol (50 g.) was condensed with phthalic acid (50 g.) with the help of aluminium chloride according to the method of Ullmann, (*Ber.*, 1919, 52, 2105). Yield 54 gms. of crude acid. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid when 34 gms. of benzoyl benzoic acid (III) melting at 223° were obtained. The mother-liquor when heated and diluted with hot water yielded 5 gms. of a crystalline acid (VII) melting at 196°.

1-Methyl-2-hydroxyanthraquinone (IX).

The benzoyl benzoic acid (III) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84) and heated on the water-bath for 30 minutes. It was then poured into water. A greenish mass was obtained which when crystallised from glacial acetic acid melted at 211-12° (yield, 5 gms.). (Found: C, 75.77; H, 4.1. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 4.2 per cent.)

Acetylation of 1-Methyl-2-hydroxyanthraquinone.

The above anthraquinone (5 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine for 4 hours. On cooling, the acetyl compound (4.5 gms.) crystallised out; m.p. 125°. (Found: C, 72.48; H, 4.4. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.8; H, 4.3 per cent.)

Oxidation of 1-Methyl-2-hydroxyanthraquinone.

The anthraquinone (4 gms.) was boiled for 4 hours with potassium ferricyanide (50 g.) and caustic potash (23 g. in 200 c.c. of water) under reflux. The solution was filtered and on acidifying with hydrochloric acid a dirty yellow precipitate was obtained. It was filtered and dissolved in sodium carbonate solution. On acidifying a yellow precipitate was obtained. It was then digested with calcium carbonate, filtered and acidified. The yellow precipitate (about 1 gm.) could not be crystallised or sublimed.

4'-Methoxy-3'-methyl-2-benzoyl-benzoic acid.

The compound (25 g.) was obtained in the usual way by dissolving the acid (III) in potassium hydroxide and adding dimethyl sulphate gradually with shaking. Yield 15 gms.. It melted at 176°.

2-Hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (IV).

4'-Methoxy-3'-methyl-2-benzoyl benzoic acid (25 g.) was dissolved in pure sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84) and heated at 155° for 30 minutes. It was then poured into ice when a dirty green mass was obtained. This was dissolved in dilute boiling potassium hydroxide solution. It was filtered and on acidifying the filtrate a greenish precipitate was obtained which crystallised from a large volume of glacial acetic acid; m. p. 299° (yield, 8 gms.).

2-Methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

The residue left in the above preparation after dissolving the mass in potassium hydroxide solution was crystallised from glacial acetic acid; m.p. 184° (yield, 1 gm.).

Acetylation of 2-Hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

The acetyl compound was prepared in the usual way by boiling with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine for 3 hours. The product crystallised from acetic anhydride and gave almost theoretical yield; m.p. 176°.

Distillation with Zinc Dust.

The hydroxy-methylanthraquinone (IV) (2 gm.) was mixed with zinc dust (100 g.) and carefully heated in a current of hydrogen. After two hours the sublimate at the front end was scraped out and boiled with sodium hydroxide but nothing went into solution. It was filtered and crystallised twice from acetic acid when beautiful yellowish flakes were obtained melting at 201°. This appeared to be identical with β -methylanthracene, m.p. 203°.

3-Methylalizarin (V).

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (2 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution (20 c.c. of 50%) and heated in a nickel crucible in an oil-bath at 200-205° for 3 to 4 hours. The reaction was complete when a small portion dissolved in potash solution with violet colour. The melt was poured in 400 c.c. of water and boiled for 30 minutes. On acidifying, a flocculent black precipitate came down. This was filtered and repeatedly treated with barium hydroxide solution till the filtrate was practically colourless. The residue was suspended in water and decomposed with hydrochloric acid. It was filtered and the residue was dried and extracted repeatedly with benzene. On evaporating off the benzene, 0.5 gm. of a yellowish mass was obtained which could not be crystallised. A portion was sublimed when beautiful yellow crystals, m.p. 245-46°, were obtained. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 3.8. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.86; H, 3.9 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative—It was prepared in the usual way, m p. 262°
The amount prepared was not sufficient for an analysis.

3-Methyl-purpurin.

Crude 3-methylalizarin (0.5 g) was dissolved in 10 c.c. of sulphuric acid (sp gr. 1.84), cooled below 15° and while stirred mechanically, 0.5 gm. of manganese dioxide was added gradually in small quantities. The reaction was complete when a small portion of reaction mixture gave a red colour with alkali. The whole mixture was poured into a litre of water and acidified with sulphurous acid when a flocculent red precipitate came down. This on purification by sublimation—it could not be crystallised from any solvent—melted at 234° Yield 0.1 gm. (Found: C, 66.3; H, 3.7. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.7 per cent.)

Acetyl derivative.—This was prepared in the usual way and melted at 287°.

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